
Functional Brain Imaging Synthesis Based on Image Decomposition and Kernel Modelling: Application to Neurodegenerative Diseases.

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2 ABSTRACT

3 The rise of neuroimaging in research and clinical practice, together with the development of
4 new machine learning techniques has strongly encouraged the Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD)
5 of different diseases and disorders. However, these algorithms are often tested in proprietary
6 datasets to which the access is limited and, therefore, a direct comparison between CAD
7 procedures is not possible. Furthermore, the sample size is often small for developing accurate
8 machine learning methods. Multi-centre initiatives are currently a very useful, although limited,
9 tool in the recruitment of large populations and standardization of CAD evaluation. Conversely,
10 we propose a brain image synthesis procedure intended to generate a new image set that
11 share characteristics with an original one. Our system focuses on nuclear imaging modalities
12 such as PET or SPECT brain images. We analyse the dataset by applying PCA to the original
13 dataset, and then model the distribution of samples in the projected eigenbrain space using a
14 Probability Density Function (PDF) estimator. Once the model has been built, we can generate
15 new coordinates on the eigenbrain space belonging to the same class, which can be then
16 projected back to the image space. The system has been evaluated on different functional
17 neuroimaging datasets assessing the: resemblance of the synthetic images with the original
18 ones, the differences between them, their generalization ability and the independence of the
19 synthetic dataset with respect to the original. The synthetic images maintain the differences

*Data used in preparation of this article were obtained from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) database (adni.loni.usc.edu). As such, the investigators within the ADNI contributed to the design and implementation of ADNI and/or provided data but did not participate in analysis or writing of this report. A complete listing of ADNI investigators can be found at: http://adni.loni.usc.edu/wp-content/uploads/how_to_apply/ADNI_Acknowledgement_List.pdf

20 between groups found at the original dataset, with no significant differences when comparing
21 them to real-world samples. Furthermore, they featured a similar performance and generalization
22 capability to that of the original dataset. These results prove that these images are suitable for
23 standardizing the evaluation of CAD pipelines, and providing data augmentation in machine
24 learning systems -e.g. in deep learning-, or even to train future professionals at medical school.

25 **Keywords:** Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Parkinson's Disease (PD), Neuroimaging, Synthesis, density estimation, data augmentation,
26 validation, evaluation

1 INTRODUCTION

27 With the rise of neuroimaging in research and practice and the development of the machine learning
28 paradigm, there has been an exponential trend in computer-aided methodologies (Frisoni et al., 2010;
29 Martinez-Murcia et al., 2016; Rathore et al., 2017). Many Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems are
30 being developed with application to structural and functional imaging in different diseases and disorders,
31 such as Alzheimer's Disease (AD) (Stoeckel et al., 2004; Illán et al., 2011; Khedher et al., 2015) or
32 Parkinson's Disease (PD) (Eckert and Edwards, 2007; Spetsieris et al., 2009; Segovia et al., 2016).
33 However, these algorithms are usually tested in proprietary datasets to which the access is limited. This
34 causes a series of problems in the evaluation of these systems, since a direct performance comparison is not
35 enough to ensure validity. Furthermore, the false discovery rate (type I error) is often high in these studies
36 due to a small sample size, significantly affecting reproducibility (Raudys and Jain, 1991; Poldrack et al.,
37 2017).

38 A useful solution to perform direct comparison between different CADs is the use of multi-centre
39 datasets, and it has already been used in several challenges, such as the CADDementia challenge (Bron
40 et al., 2015) or a recent Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) prediction challenge from Magnetic Resonance
41 Imaging (MRI) at Kaggle (Sarica et al., 2016). Multi-centre initiatives, such as the Alzheimer's Disease
42 Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) (Weiner et al., 2012), the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE)
43 (Di Martino et al., 2014) or the Parkinson's Progressions Markers Initiative (PPMI) (Marek et al., 2011)
44 provide large image samples that reduce the type I error and ease a direct comparison between systems.
45 However, this approach poses some fundamental limitations. First of all, although open data is gaining
46 support in the community ?, access to these large datasets requires the approval of principal investigators or
47 their teams, a common problem in neuroscience (Ferguson et al., 2014). Secondly, focusing on one, static
48 dataset such as the aforementioned ADNI or PPMI might increase overfitting, reducing their generalization
49 ability. And finally, inhomogeneities in scanner, population, or techniques might cause the apparition of
50 false positives that are not related to the signal (Van Horn and Toga, 2009; Pearlson, 2009).

51 For its part, synthetic datasets have been widely used in the pattern recognition community in different
52 ways. Synthetic images have all the information about how they have been generated, and so can be used
53 as a ground truth for automatic systems (Black et al., 2003; Ros et al., 2016; Varol et al., 2017). They can
54 also significantly increase the sample size in a procedure commonly known as data augmentation, via
55 analysis-synthesis (Cui et al., 2004) or performing deformations (Krizhevsky et al., 2012). This is a key
56 feature that allowed a faster development of deep learning approaches that need huge amounts of data to
57 build models.

58 In neuroimaging, some of the previous approaches have already percolated research practices. Recent
59 machine learning challenges such as the aforementioned Kaggle MCI-MRISarica et al. (2016), included
60 synthesized morphological data to prevent overfitting and *ad-hoc* model training. There are initiatives

61 to build ground-truth phantoms for developing and studying new scanner technologies (Jan et al., 2004;
 62 Segars et al., 2010; Stute et al., 2011), to study generative models of functional activation in fMRI (Yarkoni
 63 et al., 2011; Erhardt et al., 2012) or to evaluate segmentation procedures such as the BrainWeb initiative
 64 (Kwan et al., 1999). However, brain image synthesis algorithms are rarely used for standardization or data
 65 augmentation, with few examples of spatial transformations and deformations in MRI (Zhu et al., 1994;
 66 Xue et al., 2006) or SPECT-DaTSCAN (Ronneberger et al., 2015; Martinez-Murcia et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Schema of the proposed synthesis procedure.

67 In this work, we provide a novel brain synthesis technique (see Figure 1) to address the data augmentation
 68 and the ground truth problems in neuroimaging by generating a new set of images that share characteristics
 69 with a known dataset. Our system performs an analysis of that existing database and extracts a common
 70 orthogonal ‘eigenbrain’ basis of a multidimensional space where the different subjects are represented as
 71 a coordinate vector, using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), as in many neuroimaging analysis and
 72 synthesis papers (Zhu et al., 1994; Markiewicz et al., 2009; Illán et al., 2011; Khedher et al., 2015). In
 73 contrast to them, our methodology creates per-class/modality models of the statistical distribution of the
 74 coordinates in this space. Together with a random sampling based on the Cumulative Density Function
 75 (CDF), it allows us to draw new uncorrelated coordinates from each model, thus setting the ground truth.
 76 This is of special importance where class clusters overlap due to the progression of the disease (e.g., MCI
 77 and AD), providing samples for standardizing the evaluation of CAD systems.

78 We have tested this generation approach against two widely used datasets: a Positron Emission
 79 Tomography (PET) dataset from the ADNI initiative, and a Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography
 80 (SPECT) dataset using the drug DaTSCAN, from the Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI).
 81 Our purpose is to assess that the intrinsic properties of each class in these modalities is kept, while providing
 82 uncorrelated images that can effectively predict real-world samples, thus reducing bias in the evaluation of
 83 new CAD methods. Additionally, the educational use of synthetic images to train future professionals is an
 84 inviting possibility yet to explore.

2 METHODOLOGY

85 2.1 Databases and Preprocessing

86 We tested our synthesis methodology on two large datasets comprising AD and PD:

87 2.1.1 Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI)

88 The first dataset used in the preparation of this article were obtained from the Alzheimer's Disease
89 Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) (adni.loni.usc.edu). The ADNI was launched in 2003 as a public-
90 private partnership, led by Principal Investigator Michael W. Weiner, MD. The primary goal of ADNI has
91 been to test whether serial MRI, PET, other biological markers, and clinical and neuropsychological
92 assessment can be combined to measure the progression of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and
93 Alzheimer's Disease (AD). For up-to-date information on the data used, the recruitment process and
94 the image properties, see www.adni-info.org and Weiner et al. (2012).

95 For this work, we focus on the ^{18}F -FDG PET images available. This radiopharmaceutical is a glucose
96 analogue, and its distribution of the brain can be used to trace glucose metabolism, and by extension, brain
97 function. The ADNI PET subset here contains $N = 403$ images: 95 images from individuals affected by
98 AD, 207 images from MCI subjects and 101 images from Controls (NOR).

99 2.1.2 Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI)

100 Another large multi-centre dataset used in the preparation of this article was obtained from the
101 Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) database (www.ppmi-info.org/data). For up-
102 to-date information on the study, visit www.ppmi-info.org and (Marek et al., 2011; Initiative, 2010).
103 The dataset contains SPECT images obtained using the radiopharmaceutical ioflupane, also known as its
104 trade name DaTSCAN, which binds to the dopamine transporters at the striatum. This allows to quantify
105 the dopaminergic deficit associated to Parkinson's Disease (PD). In this study we use 269 DaTSCAN
106 images belonging to 111 NOR and 158 subjects affected by PD.

107 2.1.3 Database Preprocessing

108 The aforementioned datasets have been preprocessed to account for spatial and intensity differences. A
109 spatial normalization, also known as registration, has been applied to ensure that the same MNI coordinate
110 corresponds to the same spatial position inside the brain. We have used the SPM8 software (Friston et al.,
111 2007) to perform this task, using either the included PET template (for the ADNI dataset) and a custom
112 template Salas-Gonzalez et al. (2015) for the PPMI and VDLN.

113 Later, intensity normalization was applied to ensure that a direct comparison of the image function
114 encoded in the voxel intensities (dopamine transporters density in DaTSCAN and glucose metabolism in
115 FDG-PET) is possible. This corrects the individual differences (e.g., drug uptake, exposition time, etc.)
116 that affect these values, and is also key since the subsequent analysis needs directly comparable values
117 to quantify variance. We have applied a normalization to the maximum strategy (Saxena et al., 1998) in
118 the form $I' = I/I_n$, where the image intensity I is divided by I_n , the average of the top 3% intensities.
119 This normalization was proven very useful in Illán et al. (2011, 2012); Martínez-Murcia et al. (2012);
120 Martínez-Murcia et al. (2014).

121 2.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

122 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to establish a common reference, or basis, to generate new
123 images. It is very extended in analysis and feature extraction in neuroimaging (Markiewicz et al., 2009;

124 Illán et al., 2011; Khedher et al., 2015), and also was used with the same purpose of obtaining a common
125 neuroimaging reference in Zhu et al. (1994).

126 Intuitively, PCA defines a new space where the first spatial direction is defined so that it explains the
127 maximum variance in the data. The subsequent directions will try to explain the remaining variance in
128 decreasing order. All these directions, or components, are meant to be uncorrelated. This way, the maximum
129 information about the data is contained in the first components, and the remaining can be considered noise.

130 Mathematically (Brown, 2009), PCA works as an orthogonal transformation that maps a correlated set of
131 observations \mathbf{X} (in this work, our set of zero-rated images, of size $K \times N$ containing K images of length
132 N) into a set of uncorrelated data \mathbf{S} that contains K vectors in a M -dimensional space, defined by \mathbf{W} , a
133 vector whose M columns contains the basis of the new space. That way, the mapping is obtained by:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W} \quad (1)$$

134 where the columns of \mathbf{W} contain the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{X}$, the empirical covariance matrix of \mathbf{X} .

135 This is done, ideally, by obtaining the eigenvalue decomposition of the empirical covariance matrix
136 of the data. A very extended and fast way of computing \mathbf{W} , the matrix of eigenvectors, also known as
137 ‘eigenbrains’ in the neuroscience literature (Illán et al., 2011), is via the Singular Value Decomposition
138 (SVD) of \mathbf{X} :

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^* \quad (2)$$

139 where \mathbf{U} is a $K \times K$ orthogonal matrix, $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a $K \times M$ non-negative real diagonal matrix, and the
140 $M \times M$ unitary matrix \mathbf{V}^* denotes the conjugate transpose of the $M \times M$ unitary matrix \mathbf{V} . Using this
141 decomposition, we can rewrite Eq. 1 as:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma} \quad (3)$$

142 Given that the conjugate transpose of a unitary matrix is its inverse, the matrix \mathbf{W} is equivalent to \mathbf{V} . A
143 truncated version of the decomposition can also be performed, by retaining the first L components (ranked
144 by their eigenvalues):

$$\mathbf{S}_L = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W}_L \quad (4)$$

145 where \mathbf{S}_L is the truncated estimate of size $K \times L$, and \mathbf{W}_L contains only the L first columns of \mathbf{W} .
146 Since PCA does not account for random noise in its model, the noise is included as different components.
147 Therefore, a choice for L can eliminate random noise and increase the signal to noise ratio of our model. In
148 this work, when not stated, we will use the first $L = K$ components (where K is the number of samples in
149 the dataset).

150 2.3 Density Estimation

151 Once the images have been projected to the eigenbrain space, we want to generate new samples in this
152 new space, in order to synthesize new images. To do so, we assume that the coordinates of the subjects of a
153 certain class in the eigenbrain space are different realizations of a random process with a given Probability
154 Density Function (PDF).

155 In order to estimate the PDF of the process that generates the coordinates of each class, we use
156 two different density estimation procedures: a multivariate approach under the assumption of a normal
157 distribution and a per-component estimation of density using the empirical Kernel Density Estimation.

158 2.3.1 Multivariate Normal Distribution (MVN)

159 The Multivariate Normal Distribution (MVN, also known as Multivariate Gaussian Distribution) is a
 160 generalization of the random normal distribution to n dimensions.

161 Let us note \mathbf{S}^c the matrix containing only the coordinates in the eigenbrain space of the K_c individuals
 162 belonging to class c . We can estimate its multivariate PDF $\hat{f}_{mvn}^c(\mathbf{x})$ by computing the class mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}^c$
 163 and its class covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^c$. The estimation of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^c$ is performed via shrinkage, which consists in
 164 reducing the ratio between the smallest and the largest eigenvalue of the empirical covariance matrix using
 165 a shrinkage parameter α . In this work we used the method proposed in Ledoit and Wolf (2004) to estimate
 166 an optimum α that minimizes the Mean Squared Error between the estimated and the real covariance
 167 matrix. The multivariate PDF for class c would be:

$$\hat{f}_{mvn}^c(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{K_c/2} |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^c|^{1/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^c)^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^c^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^c)}{2}\right) \quad (5)$$

168 2.3.2 Kernel Density Estimation (KDE)

169 Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) is an increasingly used method to estimate the PDF of a set of data
 170 (Botev et al., 2010; Simonoff, 2012). In this case, we perform a per-component estimation of the PDF. This
 171 approach disregards conditional probabilities between components and uses each component's modelling
 172 as independent. While this is not theoretically accurate, the components extracted in PCA are uncorrelated
 173 by definition, and in practice the conditional terms are very small.

174 On the other hand, the per-component KDE is less prone to overfitting by disregarding these constraints.
 175 Additionally, the KDE can empirically account for heavy-tailed distributions that are sometimes more
 176 common in pathological models (Salas-Gonzalez et al., 2012), which might make this model more suitable.

177 An estimation of the PDF of the l^{th} coordinate of class c is defined using KDE as:

$$\hat{f}_{kde}^{l,c}(x) = \frac{1}{K_c} \sum_{i=1}^{K_c} G_h(x - \mathbf{S}_l^{i,c}) = \frac{1}{K_c h} \sum_{i=1}^{K_c} G\left(\frac{x - \mathbf{S}_l^{i,c}}{h}\right), \quad (6)$$

178 where $i = 1, \dots, K_c$, with K_c the number of subjects belonging to class c , h is the bandwidth and $\mathbf{S}_l^{i,c}$
 179 contains the l^{th} coordinate of the i^{th} subject of class c . The kernel $G(x)$ is a function of \mathbb{R}^n that must define
 180 a probability:

$$\int \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = 1 \quad (7)$$

181 It also must be centred:

$$\int \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \mathbf{x} G(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0} \quad (8)$$

182 and its covariance matrix must be close to identity:

$$\forall \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n, \|\mathbf{u}\| = 1 \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}} t^2 G(t\mathbf{u}) dt \approx 1 \quad (9)$$

183 In this work, we use a gaussian kernel $G(x) = 1/(2\pi) \exp(-\frac{1}{2}x^2)$ for the estimate. Estimation of the
184 bandwidth h is performed using the diffusion approximation proposed by Botev et al. (2010).

185 2.4 Brain Image Synthesis

186 After estimating the empirical PDF of the coordinates, we aim to generate a new set of coordinates for
187 class c $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^c$ that match the distribution of the originals. To do so, we compute the Cumulative Distribution
188 Function (CDF) from the PDF that we estimated previously as:

$$F(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f(t)dt \quad (10)$$

189 Afterwards, we can use a random number generator to provide uniformly distributed random numbers in
190 the interval $[0, 1]$. These numbers are in the range of the CDF (from 0 to 1), and therefore we can consider
191 them as $F(x)$, from which we could obtain the value x . In practice, we perform a numerical approximation
192 to the problem, in which we calculate the full CDF in a wide range of x , and then interpolate the value of x
193 using the generated $F(x)$ as query point.

194 This procedure is repeated for all coordinates $i = 1, \dots, K$ as many times as the number of subjects of
195 class c that we want to synthesize. Then, the new set of images can be reconstructed using the eigenbrain
196 basis \mathbf{W} and the new matrix of scores $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^c$.

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}^c = \hat{\mathbf{S}}^c \mathbf{W}^{-1} \quad (11)$$

197 The synthesis procedure defined here is available via the **brainSimulator** python package at <https://github.com/SiPBA/brainSimulator>, under the GPL-3+ license.

199 2.5 Validation

200 Validation of a synthetic dataset is still a matter of discussion. It depends heavily on the specific application
201 of the synthesis. For example, for synthetic phantoms (Jan et al., 2004; Segars et al., 2010; Stute et al.,
202 2011) and automatic segmentation methods (Ma et al., 1993; Kwan et al., 1999), visual inspection was
203 used. Additionally, some studies performed measures of accuracy of segmentation, but that is not our
204 case. Other studies applied spatial deformations for data augmentation (Zhu et al., 1994; Xue et al., 2006;
205 Ronneberger et al., 2015; Martinez-Murcia et al., 2017), mostly without validating the deformed images.

206 The main purpose of this work is to generate images that could have been drawn from the same population
207 of a given dataset, sharing relevant characteristics and, at the same time, being independent from the
208 existing samples. Assessing this is not trivial. Therefore, we use two kinds of analyses:

- 209 • The well-known **Statistical Parametric Mapping** analysis (SPM) (Friston et al., 2007), to obtain
210 a visual identification of the differences and similarities between classes and datasets. In particular,
211 mass-univariate two-sample t -maps were obtained using the SPM12 software, using Family-wise error
212 (FWE) correction t -threshold for a $p < 0.05$, with no masking applied.
- 213 • A classification analysis using **Voxel as Features** (VAF) (Stoeckel et al., 2004), which yields
214 classification performance on different experimental setups. We cross-validate (10-fold) a Support
215 Vector Machine Classifier (SVC) with linear kernel where the voxel intensities are used as features.
216 To estimate the SVM regularization parameter (C), we perform a grid search in an inner 5-fold

217 cross-validation loop on the training set. The following performance values are provided: accuracy
218 (acc), sensitivity (sens), specificity (spec) and their standard deviations (SD).

219 These analyses will be applied to evaluate the:

- 220 • **E1: Similarity and generalization ability** of the synthetic datasets via three different approaches:
 - 221 • **E1.1.** Assessing the **differences between classes** in both the original and the synthetic images using
222 SPM and classification analysis. Similar performance results and SPM significant areas is expected
223 if the original datasets are accurately modelled. We also study here the dependence of the synthetic
224 images on the model parameters L (number of components) and N (number of generated subjects).
 - 225 • **E1.2.** Assessing the **differences between original and synthetic datasets**, using both SPM and
226 classification analysis. If we assume that the synthetic datasets are a new sampling of the population
227 from which the original datasets were drawn, there should be no significant differences between
228 them.
 - 229 • **E1.3.** Evaluating the **predictive power of the synthetic images** on the original datasets. In this
230 case, we use the synthetic images as a training set and test de trained model on real-world samples.
- 231 • **E2: Independence of the synthetic images.** To assess how much the synthesis procedure depends on
232 the original dataset we choose a strategy based on the resubstitution error (Neto and Dougherty, 2015).
233 Resubstitution (using the training set as test set) estimates the performance loss in the training. We
234 will obtain the resubstitution error of the original training set and a synthetic dataset derived from that
235 original training set. If this performance loss is similar to the performance loss in the original test set
236 (E1.1), this means that we can consider that our synthesis algorithm produces images independent
237 from the original set.

3 RESULTS

238 3.1 E1: Similarity and generalization ability of the synthetic datasets

239 3.1.1 E1.1: Differences between classes

240 The first approach we used to verify whether the synthetic images are similar to their original counterparts
241 is to quantify and localize differences between classes in both the original and the synthetic datasets. We
242 assess this similarity using both a map of the statistical differences between classes in all these datasets
243 (SPM) and the classification performance when using the original and the synthetic images.

244 In Figure 2, we can look at the differences (t -maps, FWE corrected, $p < 0.05$) between AD and
245 NOR images with the original, and two synthesized datasets with 200 samples per class, using either
246 MVN or KDE modelling. In these maps, the differences are located in similar places in both synthesized
247 databases, that are as well, although less intense, represented in the SPM analysis of the original dataset.
248 The aforementioned regions such as the precuneus, angular, mid-temporal lobe, hippocampus, amygdala,
249 among others, are represented in both the original and synthetic datasets, with a special mention of the
250 cingulum, which also is the main difference in the MCI vs NOR scenario (see supplementary material).

251 In the PPMI dataset, the SPM analysis revealed (Figure 3) that the main differences are located in the
252 posterior part of the striatum, specifically at the posterior part of the putamen and globus pallidus. This
253 behaviour is consistent in both original and synthesized images, although with more statistical significance
254 in the case of the MVN model, and a more homogeneous distribution of the negative differences under the
255 KDE model.

Figure 2. SPM Analysis of the ADNI dataset (AD vs NOR), Family-Wise Error (FWE) corrected, with $p = 0.05$, for the original and the synthetic images.

256 The choice of these two datasets was not random. They represent two extremes of the nuclear imaging
257 spectrum: a very specific radiotracer (DaTSCAN) in two distinguishable states of a disease (PPMI) and a
258 general radiopharmaceutical (FDG PET) in a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with very overlapping
259 classes (ADNI). The separation between AD and NOR should be, therefore, higher than between the
260 intermediate MCI and the two better-defined classes. However, even the AD and NOR classes overlap in
261 the original dataset, perhaps due to a lower specificity of the biomarker (glucose metabolism) and noise in
262 the diagnostic tests, used to label the patients (Chapman et al., 2016).

263 A more descriptive analysis can be performed via the VAF performance of the original and synthetic
264 datasets. These results can be used to quantify the impact of some model parameters (for example, the
265 number of subjects generated N or the number of components L used in the model) on the differences
266 between classes. To do so, we first establish a baseline: the VAF performance of the original dataset, that
267 can be checked at Table 1.

268 Now, two of the model parameters, L and N have been varied to explore their impact on the synthetic
269 images. First, we vary L , the number of components used to synthesize images. It is logic to assume that
270 a small number of components will be insufficient to acknowledge all variance in the original dataset,
271 therefore producing low-quality images. On the other hand, a large number of components could lead
272 to overfitting, especially in the MVN model, which takes into account not only the component scores'
273 distribution, but also the relations between components.

Figure 3. SPM Analysis of the PPMI dataset (PD vs NOR), Family-Wise Error (FWE) corrected, with $p = 0.05$, for the original and the synthetic images.

Database	Scenario	acc (\pm SD)	sens (\pm SD)	spec (\pm SD)
PET ADNI	AD vs NOR	0.882 [0.012]	0.865 [0.091]	0.901 [0.118]
	MCI vs NOR	0.698 [0.042]	0.791 [0.064]	0.504 [0.179]
	MCI vs AD	0.702 [0.117]	0.444 [0.219]	0.822 [0.258]
DAT PPMI	PD vs NOR	0.923 [0.057]	0.929 [0.090]	0.918 [0.088]

Table 1. Original VAF performance of the two datasets, including MCI scenario in ADNI.

274 This evolution is assessed in Figure 4, compared to the VAF performance of the original dataset (black
 275 dashed line) and standard deviation (shadowed area). There, we can check that our assumptions were
 276 accurate. Small L s lead to inaccurate models where the VAF performance is low. On the other hand, larger
 277 L s have a stronger impact on the MVN modelling, while the KDE performance remains almost unaltered
 278 after a certain L value. This behaviour might be an indication that the MVN approach converges faster
 279 to an optimum modelling (approximate error 0.15 in ADNI and 0.08 in PPMI), and afterwards starts to
 280 produce more concentrated data clusters in the eigenbrain space due to the restrictions imposed by its
 281 L -dimensional nature. The larger the number of components L is, the more concentrated the data clusters
 282 might be, a possible indication of overfitting. We can also observe that the MVN surpasses the original

Figure 4. Evolution of the accuracy when varying the number of components L .

Figure 5. Evolution of the accuracy when varying the number of synthetic images N .

283 VAF performance with a smaller L , which points to the fact that the variability in DaTSCAN imaging is far
 284 smaller than in PET, and therefore, less components are needed for an accurate model.

285 We can assume that the optimum model uses the L that produces the more detailed images while
 286 maintaining a similar performance to the original dataset. In this work we propose to choose the highest L
 287 whose average performance remains within 1 standard deviation of the original dataset performance. In our
 288 case, it would be $L = 40$ for the FDG-PET and $L = 24$ for DaTSCAN. Now, by fixing these two L s, we
 289 will analyse how the VAF performance changes when increasing the number of synthetic images. We may
 290 assume that increasing N would reduce progressively the standard deviation of the performance estimates,
 291 converging towards the original VAF performance.

292 Figure 5 shows that, while the VAF performance of the MVN modelling increases and reduces its
 293 variance, eventually reaching the original performance, the KDE estimation hardly varies after a decent
 294 sample size (100 subjects, 50 subjects per class) has been reached.

Figure 6. Outline of the experimental setup for E1.3 to test the generalization ability of the synthetic images.

295 3.2 E1.2: Differences between original and synthetic images

296 It is now important to ensure that the synthetic images statistically belong to the same population from
 297 which the original images were drawn. To do so, we perform a SPM analysis (massive univariate t -test
 298 with FWE corrected with $p = 0.05$) that compares the original datasets to:

- 299 • KDE-synthetic (with maximum L) datasets.
- 300 • KDE-synthetic (with $L = 40/24$ for ADNI/PPMI) datasets.
- 301 • MVN-synthetic (with maximum L) datasets.
- 302 • MVN-synthetic (with $L = 40/24$ for ADNI/PPMI) datasets.

303 Therefore, eight analyses were performed (four per dataset). None of these analyses yielded significant
 304 ($p < 0.05$, FWE) differences between the two populations, regardless of the model type (MVN or KDE) or
 305 database. Therefore, the group differences between original and synthetic images were relatively sparse
 306 and of small effect sizes. This might indicate that both the original and the synthetic images belong to the
 307 same population.

308 3.3 E1.3: Generalization ability of the synthetic images

309 In the first experiment, we test how a model trained with synthetic images is able to predict real-world
 310 images. We do this by generating a synthetic training set from the original training set within the cross-
 311 validation loop, as seen in Figure 6. We tested this approach on the PET ADNI and the DAT PPMI datasets,
 312 using all PDF estimators and different L values. In each cross-validation iteration we synthesize a new set
 313 with 200 samples per class. Results are shown at Table 2.

314 The prediction accuracy, sensitivity and specificity are higher when using the MVN estimator than with
 315 the KDE in both ADNI and PPMI. The MVN modelling performance is also closer to the original baseline
 316 performance (see previous section), especially when using the suggested $L = 40$ for AD and $L = 24$ for
 317 PD. The KDE performance, however, degrades significantly when reducing the number of components.

318 Regarding the PET ADNI dataset, we tested three different scenarios: AD vs NOR, MCI vs NOR and
 319 MCI vs AD. The higher performance is obtained in the AD vs NOR, but when including MCI subjects, the

Database	Est.	L	Scenario	acc (\pm SD)	sens (\pm SD)	spec (\pm SD)
PET ADNI	MVN	403	AD vs NOR	0.852 [0.078]	0.804 [0.151]	0.900 [0.137]
			MCI vs NOR	0.688 [0.067]	0.743 [0.108]	0.572 [0.169]
			MCI vs AD	0.675 [0.121]	0.468 [0.192]	0.774 [0.224]
		40	AD vs NOR	0.790 [0.084]	0.813 [0.165]	0.770 [0.207]
			MCI vs NOR	0.496 [0.139]	0.374 [0.359]	0.750 [0.392]
			MCI vs AD	0.622 [0.152]	0.563 [0.298]	0.651 [0.320]
	KDE	403	AD vs NOR	0.770 [0.114]	0.747 [0.153]	0.790 [0.169]
			MCI vs NOR	0.642 [0.044]	0.726 [0.098]	0.472 [0.188]
			MCI vs AD	0.672 [0.081]	0.484 [0.142]	0.760 [0.187]
		40	AD vs NOR	0.622 [0.114]	0.784 [0.290]	0.459 [0.394]
			MCI vs NOR	0.509 [0.152]	0.467 [0.434]	0.599 [0.450]
			MCI vs AD	0.576 [0.170]	0.522 [0.363]	0.602 [0.390]
DAT PPMI	MVN	268	PD vs NOR	0.948 [0.041]	0.948 [0.055]	0.946 [0.064]
		24	PD vs NOR	0.925 [0.047]	0.910 [0.079]	0.945 [0.083]
	KDE	268	PD vs NOR	0.914 [0.082]	0.916 [0.113]	0.909 [0.121]
		24	PD vs NOR	0.833 [0.146]	0.834 [0.292]	0.819 [0.248]

Table 2. Performance of E1.3, demonstrating the predictive ability of the synthetic images over the real dataset.

320 results vary. In the case of the MVN estimator, the MCI vs NOR scenario performs slightly better than the
321 MCI vs AD. On the other hand, when using the KDE, MCI vs AD obtains better results than MCI vs NOR.
322 However, the big difference among them is that, whereas the MVN estimator achieves similar performance
323 to the baseline, the KDE-synthetic images lead to smaller predictive power.

324 3.4 E2: Dependence on the Original Images

325 In experiment 2 we will assess the dependence of the synthetic images on the original datasets, using
326 the resubstitution error (Neto and Dougherty, 2015). A classifier trained and tested on the same set
327 (resubstitution) usually has a low error rate (resubstitution error or training error). It is generally assumed
328 that the generalization error is the test error, or the error achieved by a test set, different from the training
329 set.

330 In this experiment, we first estimate the resubstitution accuracy ($1 -$ resubstitution error) testing on the
331 original training set, and then use that same set to synthesize (at different L s) a new test set (Figure 7).
332 Depending on the performance loss, that could imply realistic images -different from the training set- or
333 images that are almost identical to the training set -overfitting-. The results for this experiment are shown
334 at Table 3.

335 When using all available components ($L = 402$ for ADNI and $L = 268$ for PPMI) we observe that the
336 performance loss of the MVN estimator is almost null, probably due to the aforementioned overfitting.

Figure 7. Outline of the experimental setup for E2 to test the resubstitution and prediction accuracies.

337 Conversely, the KDE model produces more different images, increasing the prediction error up to a 0.2
 338 under all scenarios in ADNI and 0.15 in PPMI.

339 However, this situation changes completely when using the optimal L in the MVN synthesis. In this case,
 340 the performance loss is higher in all cases, demonstrating that the images are different from the original
 341 training set, and less concentrated than when using higher L s. Moreover, whereas the KDE achieved similar
 342 performance under all scenarios (with all L s), the MVN with optimal L replicates the baseline behaviour
 343 found at Table 1; that is, a much higher discrimination ability in AD vs NOR than when comparing to the
 344 prodromal state MCI. This is even true under the two MCI scenarios: the accuracy is higher under the MCI
 345 vs AD scenario (0.775) than in the MCI vs NOR (0.722), the same that occurred in the original dataset
 346 (0.702 and 0.698 respectively).

4 DISCUSSION

347 In this work we propose an brain image synthesis algorithm that analyses a dataset, extracts its most
 348 relevant characteristics and then generates new images that share the same properties. The algorithm is
 349 based on PCA, which defines a new common space for each dataset (the ‘eigenbrain’ space), in which the
 350 individual images are represented as points. There, it models the distribution of these points, using them
 351 to construct a generative model in the eigenbrain space. After generating new samples in the eigenbrain
 352 space, these can be inversely transform to the image space, producing new samples of the same population
 353 (see Figure 1 for a graphical representation of the procedure).

354 The use of PCA for feature extraction neuroimaging in components is widely documented (Zhu et al.,
 355 1994; Markiewicz et al., 2009; Illán et al., 2011; Khedher et al., 2015; Martinez-Murcia et al., 2016).
 356 The PCA components model different orthogonal sources of variance in the original data. In AD, these
 357 components, or eigenbrains, represent features that have been associated with the progression of the disease.
 358 The contribution of each eigenbrain (or the coordinates of each subject in the eigenbrain space) has been
 359 proven to effectively model the advance of the disease in many works. PCA has also been used to build up a
 360 reference of the sources of variance in a generative model in Zhu et al. (1994), using a different simulation
 361 strategy. Therefore, it was the optimal tool, well-known and with proven utility, to be used in this work.

362 In Figure 8 we show the first four eigenbrains (zero-centred) for the ADNI-PET dataset. The
 363 positive/negative contributions of each eigenbrain are shown in blue/red colour respectively. Each

Database	Scenario	Test (model, L)	acc [SD]	sens [SD]	spec [SD]
PET ADNI	AD vs NOR	resubs.	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]
		MVN 402	0.994 [0.003]	0.988 [0.006]	1.000 [0.007]
		KDE 402	0.811 [0.014]	0.791 [0.021]	0.832 [0.028]
		MVN 40	0.906 [0.014]	0.882 [0.020]	0.930 [0.034]
		KDE 40	0.752 [0.018]	0.736 [0.026]	0.768 [0.030]
	MCI vs NOR	resubs.	0.999 [0.001]	0.998 [0.002]	1.000 [0.001]
		MVN 402	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]
		KDE 402	0.823 [0.018]	0.843 [0.024]	0.801 [0.033]
		MVN 40	0.722 [0.021]	0.863 [0.024]	0.580 [0.143]
		KDE 40	0.692 [0.015]	0.829 [0.023]	0.556 [0.139]
MCI vs AD	resubs.	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	
	MVN 402	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	
	KDE 402	0.820 [0.014]	0.799 [0.022]	0.841 [0.030]	
	MVN 40	0.775 [0.025]	0.615 [0.047]	0.934 [0.163]	
	KDE 40	0.706 [0.011]	0.573 [0.011]	0.840 [0.135]	
DAT PPMI	PD vs NOR	resubs.	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]	1.000 [0.000]
		MVN 268	0.998 [0.002]	0.997 [0.003]	1.000 [0.003]
		KDE 268	0.848 [0.013]	0.809 [0.021]	0.887 [0.043]
		MVN 24	0.966 [0.012]	0.961 [0.018]	0.971 [0.015]
		KDE 24	0.854 [0.024]	0.839 [0.035]	0.869 [0.035]

Table 3. Performance of E2, showing the resubstitution error (resubs.) and the test error of synthetic test sets with different L s.

364 component accounts for different variability terms in the original dataset, for example, a negative
365 contribution at the cingulate gyri, precunei, and areas around the thalamus in Component 0 (Stoeckel et al.,
366 2004; Illán et al., 2011), contrast between the anterior and posterior part of the brain in Component 1 and
367 so on. Component 2 accounts for uptake differences at the angular gyrus and precuneus that have been
368 linked to AD (see SPM analysis at Section 3.1.1), also present in Component 3. These features prove
369 that the computed eigenbrains are representative of independent structures and activities that together can
370 positively influence the synthesis of new brain images via a correct parametrization and estimation of the
371 component scores.

372 The distribution of the samples in the eigenbrain space was modelled using two estimation methods:
373 a Multivariate Normal Distribution (MVN) and the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) via diffusion. An
374 accurate estimation of the distribution of the scores belonging to a certain class is paramount to obtain a
375 reliable brain image synthesis.

376 In Figure 9 we compare the two PDF estimation methods in two relevant eigenbrains: 2 and 10 (only
377 AD and NOR groups are shown for simplicity), setting the original classes histogram as reference. Note
378 that, since the MVN is multivariate in nature, we have projected the 2nd and 10th components to a single
379 component for a estimated model of $L = K$ components to obtain a clearer visualization.

Figure 8. Illustration of the first four eigenbrains of the PET ADNI dataset.

Figure 9. Comparison between the MVN and KDE PDF estimation methods for the component 2 and 10 in the PET ADNI dataset (AD and NOR groups for simplicity), setting the histogram as reference.

380 Two major features are shown in these figures: class separability and quality of the modelling. As it can
 381 be seen, a large proportion of the variability contained in component 2 correspond to class differences (see
 382 also Fig. 8 and the positive weights of AD-related brain regions). These class differences are higher in the
 383 MVN model with $L = 403$ (more concentrated classes) than in the KDE model. Furthermore, the KDE
 384 model adapts better to the empirical distribution, as it can be seen in component 10.

385 On the other hand, the scores distribution may not contain class differences, as in component 10. However,
 386 in this case, the distribution of scores in both classes is asymmetric, with longer tails and less gaussian than
 387 component 2. So, it is easier to assume that the KDE modelling will also perform better in this case.

388 Nevertheless, we cannot assume that the PCA components are statistically independent, and therefore,
 389 the KDE per-component model is deprecating substantial information. The multivariate nature of the MVN

390 does consider these possible dependences, which are then included in the model. This makes it more
 391 accurate but at the same time more prone to overfitting.

392 Overfitting in the MVN model means that, when $L \rightarrow \infty$, the model would only produce the average
 393 image of each class. So, choosing an optimum L has a strong impact on the simulated images. A higher L
 394 would contain more high frequency information, but it also overfits the model, producing images more
 395 similar to the average. On the other hand, small L s will lead to more overlapped classes, more similar to
 396 the real world, but less detail. Figure 10 shows how increasing L affects the class overlapping, reducing the
 397 variability and eventually leading to images that are very close to each other. In this work, we carefully
 398 chose $L = 40$ for ADNI and $L = 24$ for PPMI by selecting the highest number of components that obtained
 399 similar performance to the original dataset. A significantly higher performance might be considered
 400 overfitting. Other approaches to select an optimum L such as the Variance of Reconstruction Error (VRE)
 401 proposed in Mnassri et al. (2010) or the modified Bayesian model selection criterion of Kazianka and Pilz
 402 (2016) might be considered in the future.

Figure 10. Partial PDF modelling of component 2 (AD and NOR classes) using the MVN estimator with different L s. PDFs scaled for comparison.

403 A visual analysis of the synthetic images in Figures 11 and 12 reveals that the synthetic images preserve
 404 similar characteristics of the original datasets. For example, it is easy to appreciate differences in glucose
 405 metabolism in Figure 11 typically associated with AD, such as a smaller activity at the temporal lobe or a
 406 less homogeneous distribution of the radiopharmaceutical in the grey matter Stoeckel et al. (2004); Illán
 407 et al. (2011). In the synthetic DaTSCAN images (Fig. 12) differences in shape and intensity of the striatum,
 408 and bilateral differences (Lozano et al., 2010; Towey et al., 2011; Illán et al., 2012; Martínez-Murcia et al.,
 409 2014) can also be noticed, using both MVN and KDE modelling, although variability of the PD class is
 410 perhaps better modelled in KDE. This is again a probable case of overfitting.

411 When analysing the particularities of the MVN and KDE modelling under a classification analysis, we
 412 have already demonstrated that MVN tends heavily to overfitting when the number of components is high
 413 ($L = K$), but it considers all conditional probabilities in the estimation. For its part, the KDE modelling
 414 is more robust to overfitting, mainly due to its univariate nature (per-component modelling), keeping a
 415 relevant prediction ability over real-world images, at the same time that its dependence on the original

Figure 11. Examples of some original and synthetic subjects from the ADNI-PET dataset.

Figure 12. Examples of some original and synthetic subjects from the PPMI dataset.

416 dataset is reduced. However, when an optimum L is chosen, the MVN model resembles more the original
 417 dataset performance in both the generalization ability (E1.3) and the dependence of the synthetic images
 418 on the original dataset (E2).

419 Each PDF estimation method has advantages and disadvantages. The KDE modelling works ‘out of
 420 the box’, producing more heterogeneous classes and images. On the other hand, the MVN modelling
 421 requires more fine-tuning of the L parameter, but it preserves conditional probabilities that may add relevant
 422 information to the synthetic images. New multidimensional PDF models, such as a multivariate KDE
 423 estimation or alpha-stable (heavy-tailed) modelling of the non-gaussian components, could also be used to
 424 preserve these conditional probabilities and improve each component modelling.

425 Still, evaluation and data availability are currently major bottlenecks for assessing validity and comparing
 426 machine learning approaches in neuroimaging, especially with the increasingly popular deep learning
 427 approaches. Testing on large samples of dynamically generated images that belong to the same population
 428 as the original (as in E2) can produce more realistic performance estimates, leading to a standardization of
 429 the evaluation of CAD systems that provides an idea of their generalizing capacity.

430 Our methodology provides functional brain images that could be drawn from the same population as the
 431 original dataset; images that can effectively predict real world samples at the same time that they remain
 432 independent from the database used in the modelling. Compared to other widely used data augmentation
 433 procedures, such as affine or elastic deformations, it is a more advanced paradigm that can simulate
 434 functional patterns associated with a given disease, which could increase the generalization ability of our

435 models. This application is the main purpose of this paper, but apart from this there exist many application
436 possibilities yet to be explored, e.g. using the synthetic images in clinical training of future professionals,
437 or in standardized automatic evaluation procedures.

5 CONCLUSIONS

438 In this work we have proposed a novel brain synthesis algorithm that could be used, among other things, in
439 standardizing evaluation of Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems or as a data augmentation procedure.
440 The algorithm consists of an analysis of a existing dataset using Principal Component Analysis, building a
441 space defined by these principal components, or eigenbrains. In this space, we have modelled the spatial
442 distribution of each class, a model from which we can derive new coordinates in the eigenbrain space that
443 can be projected back into the original image space.

444 We have tested the algorithm in two well-known databases: one FDG-PET database from the Alzheimer's
445 Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI), and a DaTSCAN SPECT database from the Parkinson's
446 Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI). A visual analysis of the synthetic images revealed that they
447 visually resemble the originals, sharing functional patterns that have been associated with Alzheimer's
448 Disease and Parkinson's Disease in the literature. A Statistical Parametric Mapping analysis revealed
449 similar regions in both the original and the synthetic datasets when studying the significant differences
450 between classes.

451 We tested different features of the synthetic datasets under three experiments, aimed to prove their ability
452 on detecting real-world image patterns and quantifying their dependence on the original dataset and the
453 number of components used in the modelling. When comparing the two PDF estimation procedures, we
454 found that the Multivariate Normal distribution (MVN) was more accurate, but also more affected by
455 overfitting, whereas the synthesis using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) produced more overlapped
456 classes at any number of components considered, probably due to missing information about conditional
457 probabilities. Our system, regardless of the PDF estimation, proved to be a useful tool for generating
458 synthetic images that could be used for data augmentation, standardization of CAD system evaluation and
459 even educational purposes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

460 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
461 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

462 Conception or design of the work: FJM, IAI, JMG, JR. Data collection: IAI, JR, JMG, DS. Data analysis
463 and interpretation: FJM, JMG, JR. Drafting of the article: FJM, JMG, JR. Critical revision of the article:
464 FS, JMG, JR, IAI, FS, DCB, DS. Major revision of the article: FJM, JR, JMG.

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SUPPLEMENTAL DATA

490 Supplementary figures of the SPM analysis of all scenarios and datasets, including the original montages
 491 of SPM12 and the glass brain visualization, are provided in a separate file.

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